

Huanglongbing : Understanding the new threat endangering the citrus groves.

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Citrus trees are among the most important fruit trees cultivated across the world. Citrus fruits include lemons, limes, grapefruit and several other types of oranges. Citrus fruits are a rich source of phytonutrients such as carotenoids, flavonoids and polyphenols. Citrus fruits contain approximately 17 g calories, fat 0.2g, sodium 1mg, carbohydrates 5.4g, fiber 1.6g, sugars 1.5g, protein 0.6g, vitamin C 30.7mg, Potassium 80mg. Citrus fruits are better known for their fleshy juicy pulp. However, citrus production is hampered by various biotic and abiotic factors. Abiotic factors such as climatic conditions act as a critical factor in shaping the crop yield (Lobell and Field, 2007). On the other hand, biotic factors such as pest and pathogens are known to have a significant bang on crop yield and the value of production (Pimentel *et al.*, 2005). These effects result in evident yield gaps that have significant implications while taking into account the increasing demand for food and energy (Lobell *et al.*, 2009; Ittersum *et al.*, 2013) and the global food security (Strange and Scott, 2005). Among the various diseases of citrus, Huanglongbing or Citrus Greening has jeopardized citrus production in various citrus growing areas throughout the world.

HLB is regarded as one of the most devastating citrus diseases in the world (Alda, *et al.*, 2014). This disease is stretched across the citrus-growing areas worldwide. The disease is reported to cause around 30 to 100% yield loss depending upon the environmental conditions and age of the tree. In severe cases the disease can cause complete devastation in citrus groves (Bassanezi *et al.*, 2011).

1.1. Symptoms of Huanglongbing:

The major symptoms of HLB are the asymmetrical mottling of leaves, which generally display yellowing of midrib. Initially the tree shows partial decline and die back but as the disease progresses the entire canopy exhibits decline, dieback and wilting. Complete infection of the tree leads to production of yellow shoots which literally means Huanglongbing in Chinese.

Symptomatic fruit are lopsided, usually contain aborted seed, and have an off flavor. Fruit production is reduced, symptomatic fruit is small, and fruit often drops prematurely. (Lee *et al.*, 2015).

1.2. The Causal organism:

HLB or Citrus greening is caused by *Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus* or *africanus* strains. Both the strains belong to the Phytoplasmal category and are transmitted by leaf hoppers as discussed in the below section.

Phytoplasmas are plant pathogens that primarily inhabit the phloem sieve-tube, and are transmitted by insect vectors from the *Cicadelloidea* (leafhoppers) and *Fulgoroidea* (plant hoppers) families (Gasparich, 2010). These plant pathogens are associated with more than 700 diseases in several hundred of plant species, and their broad plant host range depends on the plant feeding range of their insect vectors (Namba, 2011). The Phytoplasmas that cause many fruit tree diseases are primarily transmitted by insects and grafting (Heinrich *et al.*, 2001). They are obligate symbionts of plants and insects, and in most cases require both the plant and insect hosts for their dispersal in nature. The titer of phytoplasma cells in the phloem of infected plants varies by season and plant species, and it is often very low in woody hosts, presenting a major obstacle to the diagnosis of these phytopathogens (Marzachi, 2004). The diagnosis of Huanglongbing disease is based on symptoms such as foliar blotchy mottle (Bové, 2006), as well as the use of DNA hybridization (Villechanoux *et al.*, 1992) and the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) (Lin *et al.*, 2010). These molecular techniques make it possible to accurately and rapidly diagnose *Ca. Liberibacter* spp., whereas the differentiation and classification of several hundred phytoplasma strains necessitates distinct 16S rRNA gene restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) patterns resolved by actual and/or virtual analysis (Wei *et al.*, 2008).

1.3. Variants of HLB:

Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus (Las), *Candidatus Liberibacter africanus* (Laf) and *Candidatus Liberibacter americanum* (Lam) are the three forms of HLB (Teixeira *et al.*, 2005).

Among the three variants, Asiatic form is favoured by warmer temperature; African variant is favoured by cooler temperature (Lopes *et al.*, 2009).

In South America, 'Ca. *L. asiaticus*' and 'Ca. *L. americanus*' are present in Brazil and Paraguay, while only 'Ca. *L. asiaticus*' is reported in Argentina and Colombia. Furthermore, *Diaphorina citri*, the main vector of both bacteria, has been found in all these countries, and also in Uruguay, Ecuador, and Venezuela. In the American continent, the presence of 'Ca. *L. africanus*' and its vector *Trioza erythrae* were never reported. Until recently, HLB-associated bacteria and their insect vector(s) have not been detected in Chile.

1.4. Vector of HLB:

These organisms are disseminated by insect vectors like *Diaphorina citri* the Asian citrus psyllid and *Trioza erythrae* the African citrus psyllid belonging to the psyllid's family. *Diaphorina citri* specifically transmits both the bacterial strains but *Trioza erythrae* transmits only Ca. *L. africanus*. The bacteria are transmitted is propagative and circulative in nature. Transovarial transmission is quite rare. Although there are reports claiming the sexual transmission of the bacteria by the female psyllid to the male psyllid. (Kelle and Pelz Stelinski, 2019).

The vector along with its transmitting organism manoeuvre the metabolism of host plant for their own benefit and thereby fulfil their nutritional requirement and nullify host defence responses (Nehela and Killiny, 2019).

Sometimes the bacteria are also transmitted by grafting and use of infected propagating materials. The bacteria are present on the seed coat but in the endosperm and embryo and thereby are transmitted by the seeds in any manner (Hartung *et al.*, 2010).

1.5. Management of HLB:

Antibiotics like tetracycline hydrochloride and oxytetracycline have been used on a large scale for the management of this disease. However there has been a debate over the use of these antibiotics owing to the growing concern of residual effect of these antibiotics on citrus fruits and also development of antibiotic resistant strains (Acimovic *et al.*, 2015). In addition to antibiotics, growers also prefer using insecticides to control the vector responsible for transmitting the causative agent. Systemic insecticides such as thiamethoxa, imidacloprid and clothianidin are used widely for the management of HLB. However, the recent studies reveal that HLB can be managed to some extent by continuous application of antibiotics combined with micro nutrients. Nutrients such as N, K, Mn, Zn, B and Mg are used on a large scale for raising the productivity of HLB infected plants (Morgan *et al.*, 2016).

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